

Word Sketch: An Entry Point To A Corpus For Extraction of Meaning

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Abstract

Computer aided discourse analysis has gained immense popularity because of its ability to analyse extra-large corpora in very little time. It demands a careful balance of not relying too much on the computer software to avoid overgeneralization and at the same time, minimizing human intervention to reduce the risk of subjectivity. This paper outlines the use of word sketches as a corpus technique for understanding a discourse and also targets to gain new literary insights by analysing the portrayal of SAs by the use of temporal proximity, pronominal possessors and, as Phenomenon of mental clause by the writer to convey hidden meanings. Since this research has its roots in CDA, it makes use of some of the analytical categories from socio-semantic inventory proposed by Van Leeuwen (2008) in the fictional discourse by Shamsie (2005) titled as Broken Verses. It is expected that this paper does not only provide useful insights about the fictional discourse being studied but also put forward a workable corpus methodology making use of word sketches for future researchers working in the field of CADS.

Introduction

Due to the sophisticated computer software being made available to the linguists with every passing day, new ways of extraction of information are applied in the field of corpus assisted discourse analysis. Corpus assisted discourse studies (CADS) is the term coined by Partington (2004a) for the first time and is defined by Partington, Duguid and Taylor (2013) as a branch of corpus linguistics that studies the form and function of language by incorporating computerised corpora. The next two sections explain the background of the current research.

Benefits of the Methodological Synergy

The “methodological synergy” of corpus techniques and discourse took a while to establish even after the development of techniques for corpus stylistics (Baker, 2006, p. 274). The main hurdle was the reluctance on the behalf of the discourse analysts who were interested in analyzing meaning making by studying language in the broader context whereas the corpus tools identified the smallest unit of sample corpus. Baker et al. (2008) lists the potential benefits of using these apparently contradictory approaches to the study of language. The researcher can explore much larger data sets by using computer-aided software than purely manual tools of analysis. Consequently, the large sample is representative of general language practices and supports reliable generalizations. Large samples ultimately help to reduce researchers’ bias and over-interpretations. It also improves the rigour, objectivity and validity of CDA that traditionally received the blame for cherry picking the sample (Widdowson, 1998). The corpus techniques such as frequency counts, KWIC and collocation lists help to provide statistical support to qualitative interpretations in discourse analysis. Analysing the concordance lines in large-scale data allows the researcher to move beyond local contexts towards enlarged, dynamic, and diachronic discursive contexts.

Comparison of CADS with Traditional Corpus Linguistics

Using corpus techniques for discourse analysis has many methodological differences from the traditional techniques. The most basic is the privilege given by the traditional corpus linguistics to the quantitative methods over the qualitative one. In the production of corpus assisted language dictionaries and grammars of a language, CL mainly relies on large heterogenic samples of the target language. This resulted in developing readily available corpora such as the Bank of English (BoE) and the British National Corpus (BNC), to name only two. In the past, corpus linguists were often criticized for dealing with corpus as “black box” (Gries, 2010). They faced the blame that they do not familiarise themselves with the contextual background of the sample corpus. In fact, traditional linguists encouraged that the researchers should approach the data with a mental *tabula rasa*, which reduces the risk of preconceived linguistic biasness and frees them from the baleful prejudice. Contrary to these two approaches, the aim of corpus assisted discourse studies is completely different.

Here, the researcher has to acquaint oneself with the contextual background and distinct linguistic features of the discourse under investigation. This makes essential for the discourse analysts using corpus techniques to engage with them in different ways and they cannot only rely on the quantitative aspect of wordlists and KWIC. A discourse analyst has to interpret the data qualitatively but this interpretation must be backed by quantitative proofs.

Theoretical Foundations of the Current Research

This research is founded on the theory of representation (Van Leeuwen, 2008) who proposes that actions and reactions can be represented in a discourse through certain linguistic elements to accomplish hidden communicative goals. Many social practices can be *recontextualized* and thus transformed to look commonsense but actually they harbour deep ideological meanings (Van Leeuwen, 2008). Such representations of reality contribute to (re)production and transformation of reality (Fairclough, 1992). In this research the main focus is on how the word sketch of a node word (NW) can help to understand the discursive representation through linguistic features.

Research Question

This article endeavours to elucidate the unique ways in which the word sketches generated by the software Sketch Engine can be used to uncover the social actor (henceforth SA) representation in the selected fictional discourse by Shamsie titled as *Broken Verses* (2005). By focusing on *temporal proximity*, *pronominal possessors* and SA as the phenomenon of a mental clause, this study provides guidelines for new workable corpus analytical techniques for gaining insights into discourse. This study is guided by a single broad question.

1. In what ways can we use *Word Sketch* for understanding the discursive representation of a SA?

Clarifying the Terminology

The following terms need to be explained in the context of the current research.

Temporal Proximity

Temporal proximity is a legal term but since it is not being used in that sense in this research it is essential to explain it. For the sake of this research the term *temporal proximity* simply means the words *for or relating to time*. The research assumes that the discursive construction of an action or a SA may involve association of temporal links recurrently to convey hidden meanings. This term “temporal proximity” has been used by many other linguists such as Lasersohn (1990) and Takahashi (2002) for referring to the *conceptualized closeness between the realization of a reference situation and a certain current time in any time frame* (Lasersohn, 1990, p. 1).

Pronominal Possessor

The second term which demands explanation is the *pronominal possessor*. Different linguists name the pronominal possessors in different ways. They may be called ‘possessive adjectives’ in traditional grammars (Dobrovie-Sorin, & Giurgea, 2011) or possessive affixes/suffixes (mainly in languages other than English, Haspelmath, Meeuwis & APiCS Consortium, 2013). For the sake of this research the term *pronominal possessors* is adopted because the word sketches generated by sketch Engine have a column with this name. These are a combination of a possessive adjective and the NW displayed in the last column of the word sketch (See Appendix).

Legitimation of Social Actions through Authorization

Context-specific legitimation is the most important purpose of re-contextualization of social actions. Legitimation answers the question, why should someone do this. Every system of authority uses linguistic means to establish legitimation of human experiences and social action. Van Leeuwen (2008) gives four types of linguistic legitimation important for critical evaluation of any discourse, which can be used in combination or separately in the discourse. In this research, we are only focusing on Authorization. Legitimation can be achieved by referring to personal authority, to authority of tradition or through role model authority (Leeuwen, 2008). The personal authority and the role model authority is achieved by glorifying their behaviour pattern to set future behaviour models.

Abbreviations used

SA = Social Actor

CL = Concordance Lines

SCBV = Study Corpus Broken Verses

Word Sketch: A Unique Feature of the Software Sketch Engine

Sketch Engine was developed 15 years back but word sketch is one of its recent unique techniques which can be used in a number of ways by language researchers (Kilgariff et al., 2004). Sketch Engine is corpus software that can generate a one-page summary of grammatical and collocation behaviour of any selected word

(henceforth the word selected for analysis is called node word, NW). This one-page summary is called a *word sketch* (see Appendix). A word sketch categorizes words according to its grammatical relation with other words such as all the noun/verbs/adjective predicates/prepositional phrases/pronominal possessors appearing with the NW and their frequency in the study corpus. In this process, Sketch Engine not only identifies the collocations but also assigns a syntactic ‘tag’ to the words. It relieves the researcher from analysing the behaviour of thousands of collocates, saves time and makes comparison easier. All the collocation words are hypertext and this feature facilitates the researchers to investigate the behaviour of NW further in the concordance line. The corresponding concordance lines can be generated and explored just by clicking on them. In this research the complete word sketch of the poet is added for reference in appendix. Other than that, only parts of word sketches of Omi and Samina /Mother are added for clarity in appendix.

Introduction to the Fictional World Created by Shamsie

Before starting the analysis, it seems essential to familiarize the reader with the fictional world created by Shamsie in her novel. *Broken Verses* by Shamsie is the story of a secular Pakistani feminist activist named Samina Akram whose daughter Aasmani Inqalab is searching for elusive answers about life. The plot line merges events from the personal life of Samina and *Poet* to the political world of Pakistan. Samina’s beloved *the Poet*’s literary prowess was considered threatening by the authorities. He was tortured to death by the military government in Pakistan. Shehnaz, a legendary actor and Samina’s close friend enters Aasmani’s life after 14 years of her mother Samina’s mysterious disappearance. Aasmani starts receiving secret messages and coded letters, which intrigue her to solve the puzzle of her mother’s disappearance and the *Poet*’s death.

Analysis

In this research the text of the novel is used as a corpus titled as SCBV (Study Corpus Broken Verses). The analysis illustrates the five ways of representing two SAs. In all these five ways of representation the word sketch of the node word is generated through the software Sketch Engine. In this article the two SAs focused are, *the poet/Omi* and *the Mother/Samina*. The prime focus is on the use of pronominal possessors, temporal elements and representation of a SA as a phenomenon in mental clause.

1. Representation of the SA *Poet/Omi*

- a. Establishing Role Model Authority through Temporal Proximity
- b. Physical *identification* and *appraisal* through pronominal possessors

2. Representation of the SA *Mother/Samina*

- a. Recurrent use of *Pronominal Possessors* to justify the *Controversial Social Status as Mother*
- b. Time-posting Samina’s Life through Temporal Elements
- c. *Mother* as a *Phenomenon* in the Object Position

Representation of the SA *Poet/Omi*

The character poet is the most frequently discussed character in the novel *Broken Verses*. The word sketch of the word *Poet* tells that it occurs 232 times and its moniker *Omi* occurs 146 times in SCBV. His real name is not revealed throughout the novel. *Omi* is a moniker used for the same character (the Poet) coined by the narrator of the story. In fact, it is coinage of a new word by merging the words *Old Me*. Shamsie uses a pseudo-title *the Poet* for this SA, which is a way of mixing *nomination* and *categorization*^{*}. This way this SA serves the purpose of symbolic representation of the poets of Pakistan of Bhutto and Zia’s times.

a. Establishing Role Model Authority through Temporal Proximity

Four columns in the word sketch of *Poet/Omi* were especially helpful to start the analysis (see word sketch Poet, Appendix). These are:

1. Verbs with "poet" as object,
2. Verbs with "poet" as subject
3. Pronominal Possessors of "Poet"
4. "poet" (NW) and/or ...

The next sections explain how these columns in the word sketch helped to enter the discourse and focus on selected CL to get the results quickly.

Focusing on the Collocations of the Poet

The word sketch reveals that the most frequently found verb with the word *Poet* (as a subject) is *die*, which occurs 21 times, and the most frequent noun from the same semantic field[†] is the word *death*, which appears 11 times (see Word Sketch 1 in Appendix). The other words from the same semantic field taken from the word sketch are grouped in the Table 1.

Table 1 Collocations of Poet and Omi

	Category/frame	Collocations
1	Threat to Life	Revolutionary, captive, kidnap, release, kill, rescue, imprison, die, lock, dismissive, captor, declaim

^{*}In a discourse, the SA (social actor) can be either given a unique identity, by nominating them or they can be categorized based on the functions they share with other SA. SA may be nominated by using proper nouns such as surnames and/or honorifics (Van Leeuwen, 2008)

[†]The arrangement of words into groups on the basis of an element of shared meaning. (Simon-Vandenberg & Aijmer, 2007).

	Die, death, corpse, kill, alive
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The collocations of *die* and *death* with NW *Poet* helped to understand that the poet's life is at stake. Word sketch shows the occurrence of the word *alive* with the NW 6 times. The adjectival predicate *alive* is added in the table 1 after analysing the broader context in the concordance lines. This word is used when other SAs frequently refer anxiously about the *Poet's* life or question about his life. This generally does not happen unless something unusual is feared or someone's life is threatened (see Table 2).

Table 2. CL of the word *Alive* with *Poet* in SCBV

1	fingers. My mother's kisses. <u>Hikmet</u> . The	Poet	<i>alive</i> . Someone trying to convince me – no,
2	to convince me – no, <u>Shehnaz</u> Saeed – that the	Poet	was <i>alive</i> . Why <u>Shehnaz</u> ? The words were not my
3	'd been waiting for. I was no closer. And yet, the	Poet	<i>alive</i> . Not true. Domesticity or a dildo. Larvae
4	in the fruit-bowl. And <u>Samina</u> said that when the	Poet	was <i>alive</i> she never bought peaches. She said, "
5	, last touch. It isn't as though I believed the	Poet	was <i>alive</i> . Not for a second did I believe that.
6	crack. 'Omi?' 'The Poet, Ed. Don't be thick. The	Poet	is <i>alive</i> . I know it.' 'How ...?' 'Ed, don't ask.

Use of the word *alive* to convey the meaning of death in SCBV helps to establish that focusing only on the word is not enough while analysing a discourse through corpus tools and the broader context needs to be consulted. The collocation lines of *poet* and *alive* index a variety of findings. One of them is the concern shown by all the other SAs including the *mother*, Ed, Narrator (which is a character herself in the novel), and one other *Poet*. These lines tell that the SA *Poet's* life is being referred to as a thing of past or is being questioned with concern. It also shows the mysterious circumstances under which the *Poet* disappeared without leaving a clue behind and leaving everyone speculate his merciless killing. Taking these findings as the starting point, the CL of *Poet* and different lemmas of the verb die for example *death*, *died*. It was revealed that the repetition of the phrase *after the poet died*, *when the poet died*, *before the poet died* occurs many times and it cannot be ignored (see Table 3).

Table 3 Temporal Proximity of the Poet's Death

1.	So when the Poet died it took only hours for the weavers of tales to produce their versions of what really happened .
2.	" Was it when the Poet died or when your mother disappeared ?
3.	When the Poet died – no words of his powerful enough to turn away a hammer or a fist – you saw the futility of that life you had lived so passionately .
4.	Her voice as it became when the Poet died – all hesitancy and brittleness .
5.	But because they did n't get married , and because they never really tried to hide the nature of their relationship , people thought they could say terrible things about her , and turn their backs on her when the Poet died .
6.	I stopped believing in grandness when the Poet died .
7.	" You could become the way your mother became when the Poet died , 'Dad said .
8.	' Remember <u>Beema</u> saying to your mother – this was before the Poet died , when they were back from exile and you were so happy you could hardly walk without dancing
9.	" You were saying : after the Poet died ... " Right .
10.	Even after the Poet died and the picture disappeared from her bedside , even after she left , I continued to believe the essential truth of what that picture had told me .
11.	But after the Poet died , she and my mother ... ' He stopped , unbuttoned and <u>rebuttoned</u> the cuff of his sleeve .
12.	' I remember the first time I saw your mother after the Poet died , ' he said .
13.	After the Poet died there was no reason for my mother to keep the code secret any more .
14.	But I became aware of it a few months after the Poet died .
15.	" So it's just coincidence that it happened just a few months after the Poet died ?
16.	How often had my mother been here between the Poet's death and her own disappearance ?
17.	No one except her , years later , after the Poet's death . She had only a dim memory of the card I had written for her ,
18.	You want to know if he was involved in a cover-up around the Poet's death , do n't you ?
19.	This must have been soon enough after the news of the Poet's death for me to believe I would have her to myself when the edge of grieving wore off
20.	Sometime after the Poet's death . I did keep trying , <u>Aasmaani</u> . You have to acknowledge that
21.	But here was Ed , almost delirious with panic because I had been asking questions about the Poet's death – seeing his reaction I could n't help but feel silly

This special feature of *temporal proximity* observed in the CL is called *temporalization* by (Van Leeuwen 2008). *Temporalization* is a type of *abstraction* of social actions, which can be used to highlight their importance and build them as the focal point of the whole narration (Van Leeuwen, 2008). Van Leeuwen (2008)

suggests that the discourse producer gives a sort of temporal coherence to the narration by using this technique. In case of SCBV, the narrative is divided into the events that took place before and after the death of the *Poet*. This pattern is too recurrent to be ignored in SCBV. The recurrence of phrases like *when the poet died*, *after the poet died*, and *before the poet died* make the *Poet's* death a focal point of SCBV (Table 3). Other events are positioned against this temporal anchor. Word sketch is found to be very useful in tracing this type of linguistic behaviour which may be missed by traditional corpus techniques of concordance and collocation.

b. Positive Appraisal through Pronominal Possessors

One way of appraising a SA is by making reader look at it through other SAs eyes. Negative and positive appraisal is a way of *categorizing* the SA (p.52 & 53, Van Leeuwen 2008). It is already demonstrated in previous section that the *Poet's* death is questioned with great anxiety and concern by many other SAs. In this section, we shall discuss how the column titled as *pronominal possessors* in word sketch of the word *poet* helped to understand the relation of affiliation, respect and positive appraisal existing between the poet and other SAs.

Table 4 Pronominal Possessors of SA Poet

pronominal possessors of "poet" 1.29	
our	1 7.99
your	1 6.44
my	1 4.57

The beginning point for exploring the *Poet's identification* by rest of the SAs is to analyse the *pronominal possessors* (table 4) of the word *Poet* that is the last column in the word sketch (Word sketch 1, Appendix). The pronominal possessors in table 4 can be analysed by observing the concordance lines as the table is hyper-texted. Analysing the concordance lines of the pronominal possessors of *Poet* helped to identify the following three instances where deep affiliation between the SA Aasmani Inqalab and the *Poet* is shown.

Table 5 CL of Pronominal Possessors of SA Poet

1	, and someone should tell the greatest of our	poets	that it is an embarrassment to watch a man whom we
2	was no way of arguing with that. But I knew my	Poet	. Let's say, for the sake of argument, just for
3	those damned messages from your beloved	Poet	. If it was the CEO giving you the letters, you'd
4	He lifts me up in his arms. 'She'll [Aasmani] be a	poet	, Samina . She'll make language somersault

In addition to the *pronominal possessors* the column "*poet*" and/or revealed that the SA *Poet* is framed in the greatest number with the SA *mother* in an "*and/or-relationship*" in the word sketch of both the words *Poet* and *Omi* (Table 1 & 2 in Appendix). The concordance lines of *mother- and/or-Poet* are gathered in table 6 that establishes a close bond between these two SAs.

Table 6 CL Mother and/or Poet

1.	<u>than</u> me, who knew the code? Only my mother and the	Poet	. <u>And</u> the Poet had been dead sixteen years. He had
2.	<u>work</u> , do we? Anyway, I knew your mother and the	Poet	had some code they wrote to each other in and when
3.	written years ago, by either my mother or the	Poet	<u>attempting</u> some elaborate script, why? And who
4.	My memories of those days are all about fear. The	Poet	and my mother were in Karachi at this point but I
5.	. 'She told me about that code your mother and the	Poet	<u>used</u> . She told me she thought those garbled
6.	<u>and</u> lies are the same thing. Your mother and the	Poet	, they were discreet. If you saw them in public
7.	<u>to</u> the conversation. 'Keep out of trouble. The	Poet	<u>and</u> your mother were friends of mine. I owe it to
8.	<u>have</u> let him go. We would all still be whole. The	Poet	, your mother , you, me. We would all still be
9.	still looking outside, seeing my mother and the	Poet	, and seeing himself, too, that version of
10	I had learnt in '82, the year my mother and the	Poet	moved from Colombia to Egypt and I visited them

The concordance lines in table 6 also exhibit that every time the word *mother* occurs with the word *Poet*, it is used for the character of Samina Akram only, and not for the two other mothers – Shehnaz Saeed and

Beema. Word sketch of poet helped us detect the positive appraisal of poet through the use of *pronominal possessors* and the “and/or” relationship helped to find the close bond between Poet and Samina Akram.

Representation of the SA *Mother/Samina*

Samina/Mother is the second most frequent SA in the SCBV. The most frequently used noun in the SCBV is *mother* as it is found 466 times in SCBV (Table 1). Analysing the context of this word reveals that there are three women who are referred to as a *mother* in the novel, Samina Akram (Aasmani’s mother), Shehnaz Saeed (Ed’s mother), and Beema (Rabia’s mother). Therefore, the word *mother*, which is the most frequent word in SCBV, is not used for a single SA. Analysing the wider context made it clear that the word *mother* is used 365 times for Samina Akram. Manually counting this number demands a lot of time. Word Sketch makes this job easier by helping us identify the referent of a general term like “*mother*”.

a. Recurrent Use of Pronominal Possessors to Justify the Controversial Social Status of *Mother*

In this section, the use of *pronominal possessors* to appraise the character *mother* is discussed. While observing the word sketch of *mother*, the first thing that caught my attention is the largest score assigned to the category *pronominal possessors of mother*, which is 74.03. By focusing on the pronominal possessors of “*mother*” such as *his*, *her*, *my* some very important insights can be gained about the discourse.

Table 7 Pronominal Possessors of *mother* in SCBV

pronominal possessors of "mother"		
		74.03
<i>my</i>	229	12.09
	my mother	
<i>your</i>	89	11.99
	your mother	
<i>his</i>	18	9.05
	his mother	
<i>her</i>	7	8.00
<i>their</i>	2	7.01

Table 7 tells that the pronominal possessor *my* is used 229 times with the noun *mother*. Mostly the narrator uses this expression and thus, it is used for Samina, mother of the narrator. Nevertheless, in order to be sure, we had to check the broader context to find out the referent SA by the phrase *my mother*. The 18 times usage for the pronominal possessor *his*, is always for the SA Shehnaz Saeed and the pronoun *his* is used for the SA Ed who is the only son of Shehnaz. Similarly, the word *mother* is not referring to the SA Samina when it is used as a possessor of the SA Beema (e.g. *Beema’s mother*). Similarly when it is used in combination with an apostrophe ‘s and son (e.g., *mother’s son*, is a reference to Ed) (See Table 3 Word Sketch of *Mother*, Appendix).

In SCBV Samina’s unconventional lifestyle is abstracted by changing it into a nominal group. The sorted concordance lines of *mother* reveal that whenever Aasmani talks about her iconic feminist mother, she is either justifying her actions or she is in a debate with her childhood friends and Ed, defending her mother’s actions. Use of the word *mother* too frequently for Samina is a marker that the writer wants the SA to be *relationally identified* in the role of a mother of the narrator. Table 7 shows that the SA *mother* is represented as *my mother* 299 times. The concordance lines of *my mother* tell that out of 299 time, 274 times the referent of this phrase, *my mother*, is Samina. On the other hand, she is nominated as Samina, only 63 times. This type of *possessivated relational identification* is used to show the “belonging together, and the “relationality” of the possessivated and possessing” SA (p.43, Van Leeuwen, 2008). The possessing SA in *my mother* is Aasmani and the possessed SA is Samina. In our opinion, this is one way of linguistically legitimizing the controversial position of Samina as a mother. She had opted to leave Aasmani’s father and started living with the *Poet*. She had to leave her daughter alone many a times to accompany the *Poet* when he was in exile. This is an unconventional way of living with a man and mothering in Pakistani society. In order to set her behaviour as a model Shamsie (2005) needed to justify her actions. To counter the expected criticism on Samina’s actions, she is recurrently referred to as a *mother/my mother*.

b. Use of Temporal Elements to Build Role Model Authority

A unique quality of the software Sketch Engine is that whenever a linguistic phenomenon occurs in a corpus in exceptionally large number, it appears as a separate column in the word sketch of the NW. Analysing the frequency list of SCBV had revealed that a large number of lexemes referred to the temporal dimension in

SCBV. These included year, days, time, etc. These temporal elements appeared in a symmetrical pattern with the SA Mother and Sketch Engine grouped them together (Table 8)

Table 8 Temporal Element used with the SA Mother

"mother" at ...		
		2.36
forty-three	1	11.41
forty-one	1	11.41
forty	1	11.41
thirty-eight	1	11.41
thirty-five	1	11.41
thirty-four	1	11.41
twenty-seven	1	11.41
twenty-six	1	11.41
twenty-three	1	11.41
forty-two	1	11.41
time	1	10.35

Literary conventions involve different and potentially separate time frames, which are highly artificial in nature. Unlike real life, *author time* is the time when the fictional work is originally written or published (Longo, 2016). The *narrator's time* is found inside the novel when the narrator of fiction supposedly narrates the story. *Plot time* is the time when the action depicted in the novel actually takes place and the *audience time* is when a reader reads the literary work. Sometimes these different time frames occur relatively close together, but most of the time they may not (Longo, 2016). In case of SCBV, the narrator is Aasmani – Samina's daughter who is telling her mother's story after her disappearance in the form of broken flash backs.

In SCBV, the number of words referring to the concept time are too high. In total 1028 equivalents of time are found which include words like *months, weeks, days, morning, evening, past, present, afternoon*. When these temporal elements are observed it is found that, the chronological development of story line is very rare in SCBV and random temporal progression is followed very frequently. The narration is full of flashbacks and flash-forwards. On top of it, half of the story is told through the mysterious letters received by Aasmani. Despite all this, the tempo of narrative can be traced by focusing on how much space is given to each event. A writer may choose to wrap 20 years in three lines while a 12 pages description might be given to an event only one hour long. Genette (1983) proposed the idea of *frequency* to explain the *narrative temporality of repetition*. This technique allows a narrator to return multiple times to a single event and this way its importance is highlighted. The resultant patterns of condensation and repetition of phrases referring to time helps the narrator play a sophisticated game with time. In SCBV use of temporal elements is made recurrently to represent *Samina/Mother* as a celebrity figure whose life is minutely focused. Table 9 shows the concordance lines retrieved from the column in word sketch (Table 8). With the help of hyper-texted column, word sketch made it very easy to gather the concordance lines in table 9 for confirmation of the initial claim. Table 9 confirms that Samina's appearance, dressing, interests and activities, everything is traced chronologically and given extreme importance creating her as a figure possessing charisma and extraordinary charm.

Table 9 CLTime-posting Samina's Life through Temporal Elements

1	and locked the door behind me . Here , in my mind , were so many different images of my mother . My	mother	at <i>twenty-three</i> in a white kurta , lapis lazuli at her wrist . My mother at twenty-six , unable to
2	images of my mother . My mother at twenty-three in a white kurta , lapis lazuli at her wrist . My	mother	at <i>twenty-six</i> , unable to resist an ex-lover in a grey shawl . My mother at twenty-seven ,
3	lazuili at her wrist . My mother at twenty-six , unable to resist an ex-lover in a grey shawl . My	mother	at <i>twenty-seven</i> , carrying me into a prison . My mother at thirty-four , rallying women together
4	to resist an ex-lover in a grey shawl . My mother at twenty-seven , carrying me into a prison . My	mother	at <i>thirty-four</i> , rallying women together . My mother at thirty-five , running after the Poet to
5	, carrying me into a prison . My mother at thirty-four , rallying women together . My	mother	at <i>thirty-five</i> , running after the Poet to Colombia , leaving the women and me behind . My mother
6	mother at thirty-five , running after the Poet to Colombia , leaving the women and me behind . My	mother	at <i>thirty-eight</i> , her body covered in bruises from a policeman's lathi , preparing to go out and
7	in bruises from a policeman's lathi , preparing to go out and lead another demonstration . My	mother	at <i>forty</i> , still dancing to old Donna Summers records . My mother at forty-one , allowing her
8	lead another demonstration . My mother at forty , still dancing to old Donna Summers records . My	mother	at <i>forty-one</i> , allowing her grief over the Poet to consume her . My mother at forty-two , worse
9	Summers records . My mother at forty-one , allowing her grief over the Poet to consume her . My	mother	at <i>forty-two</i> , worse than she had been the year before . My mother at forty-three , gone . What
10	over the Poet to consume her . My mother at forty-two , worse than she had been the year before . My	mother	at <i>forty-three</i> , gone . What connected all the women in those images – the activist , the mother ,

Guided by Table 9, when the rest of the text is explored it is found that there are many other words referring to time used with the SA Samina/mother. The age and number of years are mentioned not only to keep a track of Samina's whole life, especially the troubles she faced but also to glorify her life as a celebrity and a role model (Table 9). It is a common practice that the life of great people is minutely observed and recorded. Shamsie plays this time-game in which, she returns to Samina's life multiple times. **Aasmani's opinions are merged with statistics to give them an appearance of facts** and are used to provide convincing information about Samina's life. Recording Samina's age at every important event of her life adds factual weight to the story. Just like the *Poet's* death, Samina's disappearance is another important temporal anchor in the novel. One way of constructing its importance is by referring to it temporally by the repetition of the phrase fourteen years (Table 10)

Table 10CT References to Samina's Time of Disappearance

1	rather than numerical . Connect the dots , and what do you get ? When my mother had disappeared ,	fourteen	years ago , I saw dots of brightness everywhere . The universe , back then , reconfigured itself
2	I knew exactly what that ' someone ' to whom Beema wanted me to talk would say . She 'd say , it 's been	fourteen	years , Aasmaani . That 's twice the length of time a person has to be gone before they 're legally
3	I 've done all those things in the last sixteen years , though it seemed inconceivable when I was	fourteen	and he was alive . The other list , then . All the ways in which it sounds like him . Everything . The
5	was anything but hope . And it was time for the morning prayer . Every prayer of mine for the last	fourteen	years had been one single word : Mama . Every prayer and every curse . Without her here , I did n't
6	slowly up to my shoulders . ' So , tell me something . What do you believe happened to your mother	fourteen	years ago ? ' I leaned back , tipping my chair on to two legs , so that he had to let go of me to avoid
7	to look up at her . ' And you think , it can only be my mother who can bring me peace . My mother who left	fourteen	years ago , who used to leave so often before that , only my mother has that power in my life . You 're

c. **Mother as a Phenomenon in the Object Position**

The word sketch of the NW *Mother* shows many mental verbs appearing with it in the object position. These include *see, think, know, watch, hate, want, need, love, hear, idolize, fascinate* (Table 11). Halliday & Matthiessen (2014) suggest that "the 'mental' clauses are clauses of sensing and they construe events and objects

in the world as either flowing from a person's consciousness or as impinging on them” (p.no 27). They are also called clauses of perception, where the *Senser* perceives and the *Phenomenon* is being perceived. In SCBV by using this type of clauses for the *Mother* the writer gets the freedom of construing the *Phenomenon* through the consciousness of the *Senser* who is a conscious being.

Table 11CL of *Mother* as a Phenomenon in the Object Position

1.	' ' So when exactly did you <i>see</i> my mother speak in front of a crowd and fill the air with <u>grazia</u> ?
2.	<u>That 's</u> an echo of something he said when he described to me the first time he <i>saw</i> my mother .
3.	I used to drop in sometimes to <i>see</i> my mother and find her there .
4.	' I remember the first time I <i>saw</i> your mother after the Poet died , ' he said .
5.	' The door , which was slightly ajar , opened , and I <i>saw</i> my mother through it , her face grotesque with mascara tears , looking at me with such shock that I knew I had given rise to an emotion within her which she never before knew she could feel towards me .
6.	As I drove away I could see him silhouetted against the window , still looking outside , <i>seeing</i> my mother and the Poet , and seeing himself , too , that version of himself that had existed when he still thought he was unbreakable .
7.	' I thought of Ed's initial reaction to me , that moment when he stepped back as though seeing something impossible , and it struck me forcibly that he must have <i>known</i> my mother when she was in Karachi – not just through pictures in the paper or from the viewpoint of audience , but actually known her .
8.	Anyway , I <i>knew</i> your mother and the Poet had some code they wrote to each other in and when I heard you were involved with <u>Boond</u> I thought , maybe , just maybe .
9.	' ' I <i>knew</i> your mother , ' the woman said , stepping forward .
10.	I mean , I do <i>n't</i> know if you ever saw Mama do that , but <u>Shehnaz</u> got it so right ... ' ' So whoever 's keeping the Poet captive <i>knew</i> your mother .
11.	' ' Do <i>n't</i> you think I understand anything about <i>loving</i> your mother ?
12.	How can I mind that you <i>loved</i> your own mother ?
13.	' ' Why do you <i>imitate</i> your mother ?
14.	I was <i>n't</i> <i>imitating</i> your mother in <u>Boond</u>

The word sketch of *mother* (Table 3, Appendix) shows that in the *object position*, she is often portrayed as the “phenomenon” - the object of the mental process and mostly ‘I’ is the sensor of that process. The frequency and variety of mental processes associated to Samina in the object position is too large to be ignored. All of these represent her as an object of desire, love and portray her as an example that fascinates others and is followed by others. This type of *feeling, thinking, and perceiving clauses* also allow the writer to obliquely evaluate the SA in the positive light (P. 247, Halliday, Matthiessen & Halliday, 2014). Word sketch not only hinted towards the linguistic construction of *Samina/Mother* as a phenomenon in the object position but also helped to gather the textual evidences to support this claim. Word sketch helped to prove that the linguistic construction of *Samina/Mother* as the phenomenon of mental clause portrays her as an object of desire. She is valued, loved, admired and wanted by other SAs and establishes her role model authority.

Discussion

Van Leeuwen (2008) asserts that the *recontextualization* of every social action involves *legitimation*. The non-conventional lifestyle of the *Poet* and Samina needed to be justified because of the strong disapproval expected from the Pakistani Muslim society – the target audience of the novel. The question is how Shamsie has achieved this goal. Shamsie has achieved this legitimation mainly through bestowing *role model authority* and *positive evaluation* of these two SAs. Word sketches of the node words *Poet/Omi* and *Mother/Samina* revealed three important ways of representing these SAs. The pronominal possessors used for the *poet* helped us identify him as a glorified SA in the eyes of other SAs while the pronominal possessors used for *Samina/Mother* justifies her role as a mother. She is a non-conventional mother in the novel but the blame to be a neglectful mother is mitigated by using the phrase *My Mother* for her excessively. Shamsie (2005) has made use of temporal elements recurrently to show the intense threat to the life of the poet. This makes the poet’s death a temporal anchor in the novel around which all the other events revolve. Similarly excessive use of temporal elements to highlight different events in the life of *Samina/Mother* helps to bestow role model authority to her.

Conclusion

The linguistic legitimation of two SAs the Poet and Samina Akram is successfully traced in SCBV through the grammatical summary of node words. The linguistic features occurring in exceptional numbers such as temporal elements with the NW are grouped in separate columns for detailed analysis and they furthered the analysis. The discourse maker has repeatedly used *temporal link* to glorify a SA and to raise sympathy in the reader. Secondly the study establishes that the *pronominal possessors* are used to build the personality image of a SA. Thirdly it probes the discursive construction of a SA as a *phenomenon of a mental clause* to make her appear an object of desire. Word Sketch has proved to be a valuable tool in detecting and gathering the instances of *pronominal possessors*, *temporal proximity* and portrayal of the SA as a *phenomenon*.

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